

UNIVERSIDAD DE
COSTA RICA

Universidad
Rey Juan Carlos

Organizational Communication Research

Questionnaire

(Translated into English from a Spanish version)

The purpose of this questionnaire is to examine key elements of their work environment related to corporate leadership, organizational climate and aspects that affect their motivation. It is part of a research project being conducted jointly by researchers from the University of Costa Rica and the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Spain) to validate the usefulness of this tool in determining factors that affect internal corporate reputation and employer branding.

The survey will be **COMPLETELY ANONYMOUS**, so the identity of the participants will be protected. Data such as gender, age, name of the organization and time in the company will be anonymized and processed exclusively for statistical purposes. The data will be stored in a password-protected file with biometric verification systems.

By completing the following questionnaire, you are tacitly declaring your consent to participate in the research and understand that this will not imply any direct benefit or retribution.

Any questions or comments about this instrument and the processing of your personal data, as well as exercising your rights of access, rectification, opposition, erasure or limitation of processing, may be addressed to Harold Hütt Herrera (harold.hutt@ucr.ac.cr) and/or Luis M. Romero-Rodríguez (luis.romero@urjc.es).

Thank you in advance for your support.

Personal information:

Full Name:

Gender: Male () Female () Other ().

Age:

Under 18 years of age () 18-24 years of age () 25-34 years of age () 35-44 years of age ()

45-54 years old () 55-64 years old () Older than 65 years old ()

Country of residence: Costa Rica () Spain ()

Organization for which you work: _____

Position held:

Length of time working for the organization:

Less than 5 years () 6 to 10 years () 11 to 15 years () Over 15 years ()

Leadership

Please answer the following questions, in relation to **your immediate supervisor**, using a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being the highest and 1 the lowest. Please respond to the following items as appropriate, in relation to your immediate supervisor

Item	Rate				
	1	2	3	4	5
Is a person of integrity (with high ethical and moral values) and a good reputation (is recognized for having an impeccable track record).					
Is a reliable person					
Is a person who has the necessary professional competencies to perform his or her function.					
Has credibility within the organization (criteria are valued and respected)					
Is a person who demonstrates impartiality in decision making.					
Promotes teamwork					
Motivates staff					
Supports staff in achieving their goals					
Recognizes staff achievements					
Promotes good interpersonal relationships					
Values the contributions made by employees					
Keeps the staff informed of the organization's own issues					
Demonstrates ability to meet organizational and environmental challenges					
Makes it possible to reconcile work time with personal or family time					

Organizational Climate

Please mark with an X as appropriate (you can mark several options)

Which of the following do you consider to be the main benefits offered by the organization (you can check several options)?

- Competitive salary remuneration
- Company doctor
- Private medical insurance
- Canteen or restaurant vouchers
- Day care and/or support for your children's studies
- Flexible schedule
- Possibility of teleworking (hybrid or remote mode)
- Possibility to reconcile work time with personal or family time
- Solidarity association, corporate volunteering or savings and loan mechanisms.
- Team building activities
- Mental health programs
- Psychological support programs
- Financial training programs
- Possibility of growth within the organization
- Incentives for studies
- Bonuses and incentives for productivity or for meeting goals
- Other(s) - detail:

Do you consider the work environment to be:

- Optimal
- Healthy
- Acceptable
- Harmful
- Toxic

Which of the following stand out as values in the company (you can check several options):

- Punctuality
- Honesty
- Empathy
- Respect
- Respect for diversity
- Equality
- Transparency
- Other - please specify:

Do you feel identified with the organization (sense of belonging)?

- Always
- Almost always
- From time to time
- Almost never
- Never

Do you consider that equal opportunities are promoted in the organization?

- Always
- Almost always
- From time to time
- Almost never
- Never

Are you proud to work in the organization?

- Always
- Almost always
- From time to time
- Almost never
- Never

With which of the following statements do you feel more identified in your job (you can check several options):

- I feel motivated
- I feel unmotivated
- I feel anxious
- I feel serene
- I feel stressed
- I feel calm
- Stable work environment
- Unstable work environment
- I feel happy at work
- I feel unhappy at work
- I can count on my work team
- I do not have the support of my work team.
- I have the necessary resources for my work
- I do not have the necessary resources for my work
- I do not have the necessary resources for my job.
- Stable work environment
- Unstable work environment
- Conflicts are easily resolved
- It is difficult to resolve a conflict situation

- I feel in a safe environment (physically and / or psychologically)
- I do not feel in a safe environment (physically and/or psychologically).

The organization carries out training and occupational risk prevention activities.

- Always Almost always From time to time Almost never Never

Motivation

Please answer the following questions using a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 is totally agree and 1 is totally disagree.

Item	Rate				
	1	2	3	4	5
I consider that the salary is fair for the functions I perform.					
The organization supports my professional and educational development					
The organization gives me the opportunity to learn new skills.					
I am given stimulating work challenges in the organization.					
The company belongs to an attractive sector to work in					
I believe the organization will be more successful in the future.					
I clearly understand how my performance is evaluated					
I have the opportunity to be promoted internally					
I visualize myself in the future plans of the organization.					
I understand the organization's future business and action plans.					
Management is sympathetic to my personal needs and expectations.					

If you wish, you may give a brief description of how you feel in your work environment:

Thank you very much for your participation!